

Mpox Management Strategies for Effective School Administration in Nigeria

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Abstract: The paper critically looked at the strategies that school administrators can adopt to effectively manage and curtail the spread of Mpox in their respective schools in Nigeria for effective school administration. The paper depends on secondary data. The secondary data were collected from government publications, international organization documents, journals and seminar papers. Content analysis was adopted to perfect the size of the literature collected from both print and online publications. The findings of the study are that the establishment of the special committee on Mpox management, provision of funds, massive sensitization in the schools and host communities, the establishment of communication between schools and medical facilities close by and establishment of isolation rooms, provision of preventives materials and embarking on effective teaching and research on Mpox vaccinations are the Mpox Management Strategies for Effective School Administration in Nigeria. Based on these findings, the paper recommends that the federal and state governments should direct all schools in Nigeria to develop action plans on Mpox management to curb the spreading. Federal and state governments should provide special intervention funds for school for effective management of the Mpox programme in schools. An international organization like the World Health Organization should collaborate and partner with schools in Nigeria by organizing seminars and workshops for school administrators and teachers on effective ways to manage and control the spread of Mpox in schools and host communities. School administrators should provide adequate hand sanitiser, water, and face masks for teachers and students and ensure a clean and safe learning environment.

Keywords: Administration, Mpox, Management, School Administration, Strategies.

Introduction

Administration takes different dimensions such as educational administration and school administration. Educational administration looks at education at the macro level. School administration covers the following; school planning, organizing, controlling, coordinating and evaluating performance, decision making, curriculum development and planning, school plant management, student activities, teachers' programme, human capacity development, school-community relationship, academic calendar planning, extra-curriculum programme, school discipline programme, school sport, school examination and school security (Zaifada, Olowonefa, Ogunode, 2023).

School administration involves practical organization and arrangement of school work schedules in effective ways using administrative structures to implement school programmes and realize the school objectives whereby posts are created and assigned for the optimal performance of the school. School administration includes; decision-making, forecasting, school objectives, programming school activities,

budgeting, establishing and interpreting policies, examination, sporting activities, prize-giving/graduation ceremony, maintenance of school plants, time-tabling, distribution of functions to teachers, disciplinary procedure for both teachers and students, acquisition and distribution of instructional materials for the school among others. School administration operates in different forms of educational institutions. School administration occurs in the early child administration, primary school administration, secondary school administration university administration et cetera (Ogunode, Lawan, Gregory & Lawan, 2020; Ogunode 2020a).

School administration is affected by many factors such as natural disasters such as COVID-19 and Mpox virus. Educational institutions are vulnerable to problems like that because they can infest students and teachers. For instance, the Mpox virus can infect anyone – including children – if they have close, personal, often skin-to-skin contact with someone who has Mpox. In this current outbreak, most cases of Mpox have been associated with sexual contact. Although less common in the current outbreak, mpox may also spread by touching contaminated objects (such as toys or eating utensils), fabrics (clothing, bedding, sleeping mats, or towels), and surfaces that have been used by someone with Mpox.

The monkeypox virus was discovered in Denmark (1958) in monkeys kept for research. The first reported human case of Mpox was a nine-month-old boy in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (1970). Following the eradication of smallpox in 1980 and the end of smallpox vaccination worldwide, Mpox steadily emerged in central, east and west Africa. Since then, Mpox has been reported sporadically in central and east Africa (clade I) and west Africa (clade II). In 2003, an outbreak in the United States of America was linked to imported wild animals (clade II). Since 2005, thousands of cases have been reported in the Democratic Republic of the Congo every year. In 2017, Mpox re-emerged in Nigeria and continues to spread among people across the country and travellers to other destinations (WHO, 2024).

Recent data from the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control revealed that the country has recorded 318 confirmed cases of monkeypox with seven deaths since January 2024. On August 14, 2023, the World Health Organization declared that the rise in Mpox cases constitutes a public health emergency of international concern (PHEIC) following advice from the members. Mpox This implies every country and institution especially the educational institutions should put down measures to prevent the spread of Mpox. It is based on this that this paper seeks to discuss Mpox management strategies for effective school administration in Nigeria.

Concept of Mpox

Mpox is an infectious disease that can cause a painful rash, enlarged lymph nodes, fever, headache, muscle ache, back pain and low energy. Most people fully recover, but some get very sick. Mpox is caused by the monkeypox virus (MPXV). It is an enveloped double-stranded DNA virus of the *Orthopoxvirus* genus in the *Poxviridae* family, which includes variola, cowpox, vaccinia and other viruses. There are two distinct clades of the virus: clade I (with subclades Ia and Ib) and clade II (with subclades IIa and IIb) (WHO, 2024).

Mpox (formerly known as monkeypox) is a disease caused by infection with a virus, known as *Monkeypox virus*. This virus is part of the same family as the virus that causes smallpox. People with mpox often get a rash, along with other symptoms. The rash will go through several stages, including scabs, before healing. Mpox is not related to chickenpox. Mpox is a zoonotic disease, meaning it can be spread between animals and people. It is endemic, or found regularly, in parts of Central and West Africa. The virus that causes Mpox has been found in small rodents, monkeys and other animals that live in these areas (CDC, 2024).

The transmission of Mpox according to WHO (2024) Mpox spreads from person to person mainly through close contact with someone who has Mpox, including members of a household. Close contact includes skin-to-skin (such as touching or sex) and mouth-to-mouth or mouth-to-skin contact (such as kissing), and it can also include being face-to-face with someone who has Mpox (such as talking or breathing close to one another, which can generate infectious respiratory particles). People with multiple sexual partners are

at higher risk of acquiring Mpox. People can also contract Mpox from contaminated objects such as clothing or linen, through needle injuries in health care, or in community settings such as tattoo parlours. During pregnancy or birth, the virus may be passed to the baby. Contracting Mpox during pregnancy can be dangerous for the fetus or newborn infant and can lead to loss of the pregnancy, stillbirth, death of the newborn, or complications for the parent.

Mayoclinic (2024) observed that the Mpox virus causes Mpox. The virus spreads through close contact with an infected animal or person. It can spread when a person handles materials such as blankets that have been in contact with someone who has Mpox. The Mpox virus spreads from person to person through:

- Direct contact with rashes, scabs or body fluids of a person with Mpox.
- Extended close contact (more than four hours) with respiratory droplets from an infected person. This includes sexual contact.
- Clothes, sheets, blankets or other materials that have been in contact with rashes or body fluids of an infected person.
- An infected pregnant person can spread the Mpox virus to a fetus. Also, Mpox spreads from an animal to a person through: Animal bites or scratches, Wild game that is cooked for food, Products, such as skins or furs, made of infected animals and direct contact with body fluids or rashes of animals with Mpox.

According to WHO (2024), Mpox causes signs and symptoms which usually begin within a week but can start 1–21 days after exposure. Symptoms typically last 2–4 weeks but may last longer in someone with a weakened immune system. Common symptoms of Mpox are rash, fever, sore throat, headache, muscle aches, back pain, low energy and swollen lymph nodes.

For some people, the first symptom of Mpox is a rash, while others may have fever, muscle aches or sore throat first. The Mpox rash often begins on the face and spreads over the body, extending to the palms of the hands and soles of the feet. It can also start on other parts of the body where contact is made, such as the genitals. It starts as a flat sore, which develops into a blister filled with liquid that may be itchy or painful. As the rash heals, the lesions dry up, crust over and fall off. Some people may have one or a few skin lesions and others have hundreds or more. These can appear anywhere on the body including palms of hands and soles of feet, face, mouth and throat, groin and genital areas and anus. Some people also have painful swelling of their rectum (proctitis) or pain and difficulty when peeing (dysuria) or when swallowing (WHO, 2024).

People with Mpox can pass the disease on to others until all sores have healed and a new layer of skin has formed. Some people can be infected without developing any symptoms. Although getting Mpox from someone who is asymptomatic (not showing symptoms) has been reported, information is still limited on how common it is. Children, pregnant people and people with weak immune systems, including people living with HIV that is not well controlled, are at higher risk for serious illness and death due to complications from Mpox. Some people with Mpox become very sick. For example, the skin can become infected with bacteria, leading to abscesses or serious skin damage. Other complications include pneumonia; corneal infection with loss of vision; pain or difficulty swallowing; vomiting and diarrhoea causing dehydration or malnutrition; and infections of the blood (sepsis), brain (encephalitis), heart (myocarditis), rectum (proctitis), genital organs (balanitis) or urinary passages (urethritis). Mpox can be fatal in some cases (WHO, 2024).

Mpox symptoms according to Mayoclinic (2024) may start 3 to 17 days after you're exposed. The time between when you're exposed and when you have symptoms is called the incubation period. Mpox symptoms last 2 to 4 weeks and may include Fever, Skin rash, swollen lymph nodes, Headache, Muscle aches and backaches, Chills and Tiredness. About 1 to 4 days after you begin having a fever, a skin rash starts. The Mpox rash often first appears on the face, hands or feet and then spreads to other parts of the

body. But in cases linked to the outbreak that started in 2022, the rash often started in the genital area, mouth, or throat. The mpox rash goes through many stages. Flat spots turn into blisters. Then the blisters fill with pus, scab over and fall off over 2 to 4 weeks. People can spread Mpox while they have symptoms.

In this paper, Mpox is an abbreviation for Monkeypox, which is a rare viral disease transmitted from animals to humans and from humans to humans and its symptoms include fever, body pain, weakness, sore throat and rashes on the face, palms, soles of the feet, headache, muscle aches, back pain, low energy and swollen glands (lymph nodes) and other parts of the body. The virus that causes mpox is known to spread through *close, interpersonal contact*, including direct touching (including sex), or sharing items like towels and toys. The Mpox virus can spread to anyone through contact with objects, fabrics, and surfaces that have not been disinfected after use by someone with mpox. This includes items like clothing, bedding, towels, fetish gear, or sex toys. Close contact with a pet that is infected, including petting, cuddling, hugging, kissing, licking, and sharing sleeping spaces or food, can spread mpox to a person.

Possible Impact of Mpox in Schools

Mpox has the potential to affect both public and private institutions that includes, including financial institutions, tourism institutions, sports, entertainment industries, health institutions and educational institutions. The likely spread of monkeypox in schools in Nigeria may be possible because the school environment provides a good platform for the virus to thrive. If one case gets into the schools, with the school condition of over-population in most public schools, it is very easy to spread because the monkeypox virus spread by direct contact and the crowded situation within the schools provides a good environment for that wild spread. Monkeypox spreads easily in conditions where susceptible persons are close to infected individuals. Nigerian schools facilities are typified by overcrowding; making them unsafe in situations where there is an infectious disease outbreak such as monkeypox. Mpox can disrupt educational activities in schools if not managed properly.

Mpox can affect teaching and learning in schools. Mpox can affect teachers and students. Mpox can lead to school closure if not well managed by states and countries. Mpox can spread into educational institutions and affect stakeholders in the schools if necessary measures are not put down for effective management. Anyone can get Mpox in the school communities.

Mpox can affect school management, school supervision, school programmes like teaching, researching and community services and can also lead to learning loss if not properly managed in a country or state and the schools.

Mpox Management Strategies for Effective School Administration in Nigeria

There are many management strategies that school administrators can deploy to curtail the spread of Mpox in their respective schools. Some of these strategies include; the establishment of a special committee on Mpox management, provision of funds, massive sensitization in the schools and host communities, the establishment of communication between schools and medical facilities closed by and establishment of isolation rooms, provision of preventive materials and embarking on effective teaching and research on Mpox vaccinations.

Establishment of the special committee on Mpox management

To curb the spread of Mpox in educational institutions in Nigeria, each school should set up a committee on Mpox management. The above reason is because the extent of attainment or failure of any human society has its foundation in leadership at all levels (Muhammed & Ayeni, 2018). A committee that has been chosen is expected to be saddled with the responsibility of ensuring effective management of Mpox in the school. The committee should come up with action plans on awareness creation in the schools, methods, and provision of health-related facilities to be used by students and staff to ensure a clean learning environment and to work with the health team in the school. The committee should identify preventive measures to be taken and how to manage infected students in case of any.

Provision of funds

School management should provide adequate funds for the implementation of the Mpox programme or projects. Management of health-related issues in educational institutions is capital intensive. It requires a lot of funds to procure the health resources and facilities needed to keep the school environment clean and safe for teaching and learning. Funds provided for the Mpox programme implementation should be prudently used for the programme to support the effective management of Mpox in schools across Nigeria. This development is capable of enhancing long-term satisfaction (Ayeni, Doosuur, & Kefas, 2021).

Massive sensitization in the schools and host communities

School management is saddled with the responsibility of providing adequate health information and communication to their teachers and students within the schools and also to the host communities. This sensitization will form effective communication that can enhance peacebuilding, which implies that people will be better off and not worse off (Ayeni, Sani, & Uzoigwe, 2019). The school through the medical team or committee is expected to provide adequate information on Mpox to the students, teachers and host communities to prevent the spread of Mpox. Relevant information on the origin of Mpox, The students should be taught that the Mpox virus can spread to anyone through contact with objects, fabrics, and surfaces that have not been disinfected after use by someone with Mpox. This includes items like clothing, bedding, towels, fetish gear, or sex toys. Close contact with a pet that is infected, including petting, cuddling, hugging, kissing, licking, and sharing sleeping spaces or food, can spread Mpox to a person.

The setting of schools, especially tertiary institutions is expected to enhance socio-economic development in the community where such school is located (Ayeni, & Ezirim, 2023). Students and host communities should know that Mpox spreads can occur when they come into contact with an animal or a person infected with the virus. Person-to-person spread (transmission) occurs when they come in contact with the sores, scabs, respiratory droplets or oral fluids of a person who's infected, usually through close, intimate situations like cuddling, kissing or sex.

Students and host communities should be taught ways to prevent Mpox which includes; vaccination, other ways to help prevent the spread of Mpox include: Avoiding contact with infected animals (especially sick or dead animals). Avoid contact with bedding and other materials contaminated with the virus. Thoroughly cooking all foods that contain animal meat or parts. Washing hands frequently with soap and water. Avoiding contact with people who may be infected with the virus. Practising safe sex, including the use of condoms and dental dams. Wearing a mask that covers your mouth and nose when around others. Cleaning and disinfecting frequently touched surfaces and using personal protective equipment (PPE) when caring for people infected with the virus.

Establishment of communication between schools and medical facilities around

School management through the medical team should establish communication with any approved medical facilities to aid fast responses in case of any identification of any teacher or students having Mpox in the schools. This will help to isolate the person and to trace contact in the schools.

Establishment of isolation room

School management should establish isolation rooms or centres in case of any report of Mpox or other related health problems in the schools. The isolated rooms or centres will assist the school in keeping the infected person from others to avoid spreading the disease. Isolation rooms as an infrastructure that can prevent the spread of diseases, this is because the provision of infrastructure enhances the wellbeing of the people (Ayeni & Sani, 2021; Ayeni, 2024). To prevent the spread of Mpox to others, people with Mpox should isolate at home following guidance from their health care provider, or in the hospital where there is an isolation room if needed, for the duration of the infectious period (from onset of symptoms until lesions have healed and scabs fall off). The government should provide facilities that can help curtail the spread of these diseases because the government must provide those facilities that help people (Ayeni,

Sani, Idris, & Uzoigwe, 2019). Covering lesions and wearing a well-fitting mask when in the presence of others may help prevent spread (CDC 2024).

Provision of preventive materials

School management should provide all necessary materials and resources needed to keep the school clean from infection. Schools should adequate handwashing supplies, including soap and water, maintain routine cleaning and disinfection practices (including cleaning sports gear and laundering uniforms), identifying private spaces for assessment of an ill child away from others, and provision of personal protective equipment (PPE) for staff who care for students with infectious diseases (CDC 2024). School management should provide; soap and water, alcohol-based hand sanitiser, face masks, Waste Disposal and gloves and gowns. The provision of disease-preventive materials needs funding. Thus, it has been argued that money is the lifeblood of every human society (Ayeni, 2017). The failure of the government to provide funds for the purchase of disease-preventive materials can result in serious problems for the education system. This is why scholars have argued that the inability of the governance system to perform its roles is also hurting the educational system (Ogunode, Ayeni, & Olorundare, 2024; Ayeni & Nwaorgu, 2018).

Effective teaching

School management should ensure an effective teaching programme on Mpox. Teachers in educational institutions should be trained on measures and management measures to prevent Mpox. Federal and state ministries of education should train teachers to equip them with the right knowledge of Mpox. The foregoing is because training improves the performance of individuals on their jobs by correcting any deficiency in human effort (Ogunode & Ayeni, 2023). The teachers should be directed to guide the students on preventive behaviour to adopt to curtail the spread of Mpox in the schools and the communities. The schools should ensure students are taught to avoid close, skin-to-skin contact with people who have a rash that looks like mpox. This includes intimate contact, like hugging, kissing, or other skin-to-skin contact. Avoid sharing objects like bedding, towels, clothing, or utensils with someone who has mpox.

Research on Mpox vaccinations

School management especially the tertiary institutions can engage in research on Mpox management and treatment since research is the second cardinal programme of the tertiary institutions. This is one of the reasons why tertiary education is viewed as post-basic and secondary school education that embraces advanced teaching, research and community service (Ogunode, Ayeni, & Ogwuche, 2024). Tertiary institutions through their researchers and post-graduate students can engage in varieties of research on Mpox treatment, management and Mpox vaccinations. Research findings from these researches can be useful for policy-making and can lead to better ways of Mpox vaccinations and treatment in Nigeria and other countries. Tertiary institutions have a great role to play in the management strategies of Mpox in the schools and the entire nation.

Findings

The paper revealed that **the** establishment of the special committee on Mpox management, provision of funds, massive sensitization in the schools and host communities, the establishment of communication between schools and medical facilities close by and establishment of the isolation room, provision of preventive materials and embarking on effective teaching and research on Mpox vaccinations are some of the strategies school administrators can adopt to curtail the spread of Mpox in Nigerian schools.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The paper concluded that the establishment of the special committee on Mpox management, provision of funds, massive sensitization in the schools and host communities, the establishment of communication between schools and medical facilities close by and establishment of isolation rooms, provision of preventives materials and embarking on effective teaching and research on Mpox vaccinations.

Based on these findings, the paper recommends that the federal and state governments should direct all schools in Nigeria to develop action plans on Mpox management to curb the spreading. Federal and state governments should provide special intervention funds for school for effective management of the Mpox programme in schools. An international organization like the World Health Organization should collaborate and partner with schools in Nigeria by organizing seminars and workshops for school administrators and teachers on effective ways to manage and control the spread of Mpox in schools and host communities. School administrators should provide adequate hand sanitiser, water, and face marks for teachers and students and ensure a clean and safe learning environment.

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